

Thermoosmosis in Membranes

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The theories proposed to interpret the process of thermoosmosis (chiefly of liquids) in membranes have been critically examined. The limitations of the thermodynamic approach have been pointed out, and the scope of the radiation pressure theory (originally proposed to deal with thermoosmosis of macromolecular solutions) in coupled transport processes discussed. The significance of membrane-water interactions has been highlighted in terms of the phenomenon of epitaxis. The discrepancies existing in the experimental results are attributed to the neglect in the classical theories of the membrane factor. The review is concluded with a mention of the possible role of thermoosmosis in living systems.

WHEN a temperature gradient is imposed across a membrane separating two adjacent portions of a fluid or in general, a multicomponent solution, each of which is uniform by itself, the flow of thermal energy induces a mass flow through the membrane by way of coupling. Such migrations are referred to as "thermoosmosis".

Lippman¹ and Aubert² first reported appreciable thermoosmosis of water and electrolyte solutions through a number of membranes. They considered the thermoosmosis of electrolytes across charged membranes as a electrochemical phenomenon and related to electroosmosis. This view was later supported by Sollner and his co-workers³. The work of Ernst and Koczkas^{4,5} was criticised by Ursprung⁶ and need not be considered here. Derjaguin and Sidorenkov⁷ reported results on thermoosmosis of water and other liquids through sintered glass filters. These experiments were repeated (and expanded) by Denbigh *et al*⁸, who concluded that much of the previously reported effect was due to thermal expansion. Further, they were of the opinion that the sure cases of thermoosmosis involved some electrokinetic mechanism and can not be explained on the basis of classical thermodynamics.

Denbigh and co-workers also studied the thermoosmotic flow of various gases through rubber membranes⁹. Similar studies, using different membranes, were conducted by Mason *et al*^{10,11,12,13}, Hanby^{14,15,16}, Rastogi *et al*¹⁷, and others.

Meanwhile, Haase¹⁸⁻²³ performed thermoosmotic experiments with pure liquids, and solutions of non-electrolytes and presented theoretical considerations. Similar studies involving liquid systems were conducted by Rastogi and Singh²⁴, Dariel and Kedem²⁵, and more recently by Gaeta and Mita²⁶⁻²⁹, who worked with solutions of macromolecules and developed the "radiation pressure theory" to account for their results.

Whereas the diffusion of gases through porous membranes under the influence of a temperature gradient has been extensively studied and is amenable to the existing theoretical treatments, the corresponding phenomenon with liquids is a subject of controversy at both theoretical and experimental levels. An agreement between theoretical predictions and experimental results is also lacking in some cases. This has been appropriately expressed by Haase¹⁸ who maintained that only a few, and in part questionable, observations on thermoosmosis in liquid systems were extant. In the present review, therefore, thermoosmotic experiments conducted, and results obtained with liquids will be examined mainly with only a passing reference to the experiments involving gases, a field more exact, and thoroughly discussed as compared to the situation with liquids.

Theories of thermoosmosis :

It is accepted that the membrane in thermoosmosis experiments acts as a seat of the phenomenon of thermal diffusion and therefore, theories proposed to deal with the latter, have been considered in connection with thermoosmosis too. Such theories, by their very nature, pay scant attention to the nature of the membrane and the interaction of the latter with the diffusing substance, and obviously this constitutes the greatest lacuna of these theories. The "radiation pressure" theory makes an attempt to take into consideration the specific membrane interactions.

Although the process of thermal diffusion in condensed phases ("Soret effect") has been studied for many years and several theories, starting with van't Hoff's osmotic pressure theory³⁰, have been put forward from time to time, the situation is still far from well understood. Most of these earlier theories, which include some rather involved kinetic theories due to Wirtz and Hiiby³¹, Alexander³²,

Denbigh³³, Drickamer³⁴ and others will be skipped off (these theories are reviewed by Sanyal³⁵) and we shall refer to the most general theory dealing with such non-isothermal transport processes, namely the non equilibrium thermodynamic theory, based on Onsager's Reciprocity Relations (O.R.R.). In a simple treatment of this theory, all gradients in temperature and chemical potentials (if any) are supposed to be confined within the membrane phase (which may be attained by keeping each bulk phase thoroughly mixed). Furthermore, a state of thermodynamic equilibrium with respect to temperature and partitioning of solutes is assumed to exist between the bulk phase and the membrane at each interface. The temperature gradient across the membrane is also considered linear within the latter. It is often difficult to realise these requirements in practice, and in particular, existence of unstirred Nernst's layers in the vicinity of the membrane interfaces has been proposed³⁶, the net effect of which is to diffuse (and reduce) the effective temperature gradient across the membrane.

With this back-ground, we may proceed to formulate the linear phenomenological equations for flux densities through the membrane in terms of the language of irreversible thermodynamics. The treatment given follows that of Sanyal and Adhikari³⁷ which deals, in detail, with the essential features of the theory. The following is an extension of this theory to membrane-transport.

If J_1 and J_2 are the flux densities of heat and matter, respectively, and X_1 and X_2 , the corresponding driving (thermodynamic) forces, then

$$J_1 = L_{11}X_1 + L_{12}X_2 \quad \dots (1)$$

$$J_2 = L_{21}X_1 + L_{22}X_2 \quad \dots (2)$$

Here, $J_{membrane} = 0$ defines the reference frame for J_1 and J_2 . L_{11} and L_{22} are the "direct" phenomenological coefficients for the independent processes of thermal conduction (L_{11} is related to the thermal conductivity of the membrane phase) and diffusion through the membrane, while L_{12} and L_{21} are the "cross-effect" coefficients representing coupling between the two flows in the membrane phase. The fluxes and the forces are so chosen as to be linearly independent and to satisfy the following relation ;

$$\sigma \propto (J_1X_1 + J_2X_2)$$

where σ is the rate of entropy production (due to irreversible processes occurring) per unit volume of the system. The purpose of such a choice for J 's and X 's is to ensure the applicability of O.R.R between the cross-effect coefficients, namely the equality,

$$L_{12} = L_{21} \quad \dots (3)$$

Relations of this type (viz. eq. 3) greatly reduce the number of independent phenomenological coefficients to be determined by experiment in any coupled transport process, and hence are advantageous.

These linear relations between J 's and X 's, viz. eqs. (1) and (2), are in fact the limiting cases, valid only for small values of the forces, of more general non-linear phenomenological equations. The latter depends, for their application in practical systems, on the symmetry of the matrix of higher-order phenomenological coefficients in addition to Onsager's relations³⁷.

For the case of thermoosmosis of a gas through a porous partition, we can define the forces as follows (ideal gas behaviour assumed) ;

$$X_1 = -\frac{1}{T} \cdot \frac{dT}{dx} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$X_2 = -\frac{RT}{p} \cdot \frac{dp}{dx} \quad \dots (5)$$

where p is the gas pressure (the gas in the bulk is supposed to be in equilibrium with the membrane interface saturated with this gas).

Evidently, when $X_1 = 0$, it follows from eqs. (1) and (2)

$$J_1 = L_{12}X_2 = -L_{22} \frac{RT}{p} \cdot \frac{dp}{dx} \quad \dots (6)$$

and

$$J_2 = L_{22}X_2 = -L_{12} \frac{RT}{p} \cdot \frac{dp}{dx} \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\text{Thus, } \left(\frac{J_1}{J_2}\right)_{X_1=0} = \frac{L_{12}}{L_{22}} ; \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\text{or, } J_1 = \frac{L_{12}}{L_{22}} J_2 \text{ under isothermal conditions.}$$

We now introduce the heat of transport $\hat{Q}$ as the amount of heat absorbed per mole of a diffusing substance from the region it leaves and released in the region it moves into, under isothermal conditions (and with migration of no other component in a polycomponent system), i.e.,

$$\hat{Q} = \left(\frac{J_1}{J_2}\right)_{X_1=0} = \frac{L_{12}}{L_{22}} \text{ from eq (8)} \quad \dots (9)$$

A detailed discussion leading to physical insight into $\hat{Q}$ has recently been given by Sanyal and Adhikari³⁷.

Now, at the steady state, $J_2 = 0$, and by using O.R.R., viz. eq. (3), we obtain from eq. (2)

$$L_{21} X_1 = -L_{22} X_2$$

$$\text{i.e., } \left(\frac{X_2}{X_1}\right)_{st} = -\frac{L_{21}}{L_{22}} = -\frac{L_{12}}{L_{22}} = -\hat{Q} \quad \dots (10)$$

(from eq. 9)

(the subscript 'st' denotes the steady state). Substituting eqs. (4) and (5) into eq. (10),

$$\hat{Q} = -\frac{RT^2}{p} \cdot \frac{dp}{dT} \quad \dots (11)$$

Using $p=RT/\bar{V}$, one obtains from eq. (11)

$$\left(\frac{dp}{dT}\right)_{s,t} = -\frac{Q}{\bar{V}} \quad \dots (12)$$

where $\bar{V}$ is the molar volume of the diffusing gas, and T , the mean temperature, here $(dp/dT)_{s,t}$ refers to the steady state value across the membrane. A similarity between eq. (12) and the Clapeyron's equation for isothermal phase-transition in reversible thermodynamics is worth noting.

It must be emphasised at this stage that such thermoosmosis, although somewhat analogous in its microscopic aspects to the thermal effusion of gases, is clearly distinct from the latter; the effusion always leads to the higher pressure of gas on the warmer side of the membrane, while in thermoosmosis, various gases behave differently and hydrogen, in particular, accumulates on the cooler side of a rubber membrane⁹. Rastogi *et al*¹⁷ distinguished in this context, between viscous flow of a gas through a membrane and the corresponding thermal migration by setting two limits to $\hat{Q}$ values. Thus, if λ be the mean free path of a gas molecule, and a the diameter of a typical pore in the membrane the kinetic theory predicts that,

$$\lim_{(a/\lambda) \rightarrow 0} \hat{Q} = -RT/2 \text{ (Knudsen limit),}$$

$$\lim_{(a/\lambda) \rightarrow \infty} \hat{Q} = 0 \text{ (Poiseuille limit).}$$

Cases of intermediate (a/λ) values are much more complicated. In particular, there is normally some interaction between the gas and the membrane-substance which tends substantially to modify the value of the heat of transport by adding a heat of solution term to it. It is to this latter type of membrane-transport processes that the term thermoosmosis is generally applied.

One has to turn to the kinetic theory, however, in order to assign physical meaning to the first order (and higher order) phenomenological coefficients. Denbigh and Raumann⁹ first developed such a theory for the transient approach to the steady state, which was later generalised by Crowe³⁸ to cases of differing and changing gas volumes. More recently, Mason and Evans¹⁰⁻¹³ have advanced the "dusty model", a general theoretical approach in which the porous medium is visualised as a collection of stationary "dust" particles.

It is worth emphasising here that the choice of the thermodynamic forces X_1 and X_2 is not arbitrary and it needs to be pointed out that some authors have erroneously defined temperature and pressure differences across the membrane as forces, instead of the corresponding gradients.

In the following sections, experimental results, obtained by various workers, will be introduced and the reasons for discrepancies will be discussed.

Experiments on thermoosmosis of gases :

Although the treatment of the previous section is generally adequate for interpreting the results of thermoosmotic experiments with gases, discrepancies were noted between $\hat{Q}$, obtained from the steady state equation, viz. eq. (12), and those determined from isothermal and thermoosmotic permeabilities^{14,15}. Introduction of the second-order phenomenological coefficients does sometimes lead to better agreements. According to Hanley and Steele^{16,19}, the difference between the "true" $\hat{Q}$ and the steady state value of $\hat{Q}$ passes through a maximum at $(a/\lambda) \approx 0.2$, and tends to small values for $(a/\lambda) < 0.9$.

Conflicting values of $\hat{Q}$ have sometimes been recorded by various workers. Thus, Rastogi¹⁷ reports 62.77 cal. mol⁻¹ (the mean temperature T_m used=327 K) as $\hat{Q}$ for thermoosmosis of CO₂ through unglazed porcelain, while Denbigh and Raumann⁹ obtained a value of 1860 cal. mol⁻¹ ($T_m=304.3$ K), and Bearman^{39,40} got 980 cal. mol⁻¹ ($T_m=318$ K). Further, Rastogi observed no dependence of $\hat{Q}$ on the mean temperature of the experiment, in total conflict with eq. (12).

Experiments on thermoosmosis of liquids :

As briefly mentioned earlier, Haase¹⁸⁻²³ and co-workers conducted extensive studies on thermoosmosis of water through cellophane 300 and 600 membranes. More recently, they have extended their study to methanol-cellophane systems.

In his experiments with cellophane 600 membranes, Haase²² reports an almost linear dependence of $\hat{Q}$ on T_m over a wide range of mean temperatures (10° to 90°) with $\hat{Q}$ being a monotone-decreasing function of T_m and its sign reversing at 55° to 60°.

Such a linear variation of $\hat{Q}$ with T_m over a wide range of temperatures is unexpected since the phenomenological coefficients are unlikely to remain linear in that range. As for the conflicting results, Rastogi and Singh²⁴, who also studied thermoosmosis through cellophane membranes, reports a $\hat{Q}$ equal to 0.120 cal. mol⁻¹ at $T_m=46^\circ$ for water across cellophane while Haase²² finds 0.535 cal. mol⁻¹ at $T_m=45.42^\circ$. At $T_m=50^\circ$, Rastogi observed $\hat{Q}=0.090$ cal. mol⁻¹, while the corresponding value reported by Haase is 0.240 cal. mol⁻¹ at $T_m=50.84^\circ$.

Finally, at $T_m=54^\circ$, Rastogi's value for $\hat{Q}$ is 0.130 cal. mol⁻¹ whereas that of Haase is 0.0178 cal. mol⁻¹ at $T_m=55.51^\circ$.

As one moves on to methanol-cellophane system, the situation becomes even worse. Thus, Rastogi²⁴ obtains the value of $\hat{Q}=+1.53$ cal. mol⁻¹ at $T_m=42^\circ$ as against Haase's²³ -0.885 cal. mol⁻¹ at $T_m=43.77^\circ$. In fact, Haase reports negative $\hat{Q}$ values

for all the mean temperatures from 9.32° to 59.15°. Both these authors appear to have defined their thermodynamic forces erroneously in that ΔP and ΔT (which they consider as forces) are not true "gradients".

In their study of thermoosmosis in the presence, as well as absence, of an osmotic pressure difference, using cellulose acetate membranes, with aqueous sodium chloride and pure water on the hot and the cold side, respectively, Dariel and Kedem²⁵ report enormously high values of $\hat{Q}$ for water. At 25°, they obtained $\hat{Q}=390$ cal. mol⁻¹ compared to Haase's²¹ 1.72 cal. mol⁻¹ at $T_m=25.33^\circ$. At 45°, they get 440 cal. mol⁻¹, while Haase obtains 0.535 cal. mol⁻¹ for $T_m=45.42^\circ$, and Rastogi reports 0.120 cal. mol⁻¹ at 46°. Furthermore, Dariel and Kedem's heat of transport is an increasing function of temperature, T_m , while Haase's $\hat{Q}$ decreases with T_m . It is noteworthy that both Haase and Rastogi appear to have neglected the temperature drops in their solutions, whereas Dariel and Kedem have made an allowance for such lowering of temperature.

Thermoosmosis of macromolecular solutions : Radiation pressure theory :

In recent years, Gaeta and his associates²⁶⁻²⁹, have developed the "radiation pressure theory" to account for the thermodiffusive phenomena in condensed phases. Based on the original idea of Debye⁴¹ that the thermal energy in liquids can be represented as an ensemble of elastic longitudinal waves of very high frequency ("Debye waves"), this theory proposes that the flow of heat in liquids produces a flux of mechanical momentum which is proportional to the "momentum conductivity" of the fluid. The latter is the ratio of thermal conductivity to the velocity of elastic waves (sound waves) in the medium itself. Consequently, the continuous flow of these "thermal waves" from the hot to the cold side in a non-isothermal solution results in a force that acts on the dissolved (or, suspended) particles in the absence of convection. The direction of this force is parallel to the temperature gradient, and its magnitude is given by²⁶

$$F = 2\tau_{l,p} \left(\frac{k_l}{v_l} - \frac{k_p}{v_p} \right) \sigma' \frac{dT}{dx} \quad \dots (13)$$

where $\tau_{l,p}$ is the characteristic coefficient of transmission of elastic waves from the liquid to the material the particles are made of; k_l , v_l and k_p , v_p are the thermal conductivity and velocity of sound in the liquid and in the particles, respectively, (obviously, k/v is taken as the momentum conductivity); σ' is the cross sectional surface area of a given particle and (dT/dx) , is the temperature gradient. The sign of the force F , and consequently, the direction of migration of the solute, depends upon the sign of the expression,

$$\left(\frac{k_l}{v_l} - \frac{k_p}{v_p} \right) \quad \dots (14)$$

Gaeta²⁷ further obtained a relation between the Soret coefficient S^{25} and the molecular weight M of the solute as

$$S = HM^{2/3} \quad \dots (15)$$

where H is a constant dependent on the geometry and the density of the solute particles.

According to this theory, thermal diffusion is a consequence of a mechanical interaction of thermal elastic waves with matter.

Gaeta and co-workers have applied the radiation-pressure approach to a number of systems, mostly solutions of high molecular weight biologically important compounds with considerable success. However, in view of the lack of data on the values of k and/or v , in various solvents and solute materials, it does not seem possible at present to fully evaluate the validity of this approach. Moreover, the macroscopic nature of the quantities k and v adds another difficulty to the direct application of the theory to solutions of molecular, rather than macromolecular particles.

Recently, Gaeta and Mita²⁹ have extended the radiation-pressure theory to thermoosmosis (which they have named "thermodialysis") of liquids. In particular, they have stressed the importance of "epitaxis", the adsorption of solvent molecules on the pore-walls of the thermoosmotic membrane, leading to the formation of thin layers of sorbed solvent with physicochemical properties, very different from those of the bulk solvent in the larger pores of the membrane. Depending on the nature and magnitude of the solvent-membrane interaction, the sign of the expression,

$$\left[\left(\frac{k}{v} \right)_{l*} \left(\frac{dT}{dx} \right)_{l*} - \left(\frac{k}{v} \right)_p \left(\frac{dT}{dx} \right)_p \right] \quad \dots (16)$$

where l^* stands for the "epitaxed liquid" will be positive, or negative, and consequently, the solute particles will migrate to the cold, or hot side of the membrane, respectively. In this way, they have been able to account for the direction of solute flow in a number of systems, and have provided an explanation for the reversal of flow of polyvinyl polymers (in 1-butanol solvent) across nucleopore membranes of gradually decreasing pore-size so that the effect of epitaxis (i.e., of eq. 16) also becomes progressively more important.

Discussion

a) *Sources of error* : It does not appear quite simple to locate the possible sources of error which have caused such enormous discrepancies between the results of different investigators. In some cases, however, much could have been desired to ensure better experimental arrangements. Thus, in one particular case¹⁷, no thermostat was used to regulate the temperature of each compartment containing the diffusing gas. In the thermoosmosis of liquids, some error appears inevitable while measuring the

amount of flow and the hydrostatic pressure difference through the use of capillaries which protrude out of the thermostated region, and are therefore exposed to the temperature fluctuations of the atmosphere. Moreover, it is difficult to allow for the differential thermal expansion in such non-isothermal experiments while monitoring the movement of the liquid meniscus in exposed capillaries unless the temperature of the liquid in the capillaries are known precisely.

Another problem is the presence of unstirred layers and the difficulty in maintaining a uniform temperature in the proximity of the membrane, even under conditions of vigorous stirring⁴².

Perhaps the most important of all the considerations, but much neglected to date, is the overwhelming dependence of the phenomenon on the nature of the membrane. Not only the membrane alters the magnitude of the effect, but it can even change its direction²⁹.

(b) *Importance of epitaxis* : While discussing the significance of the "membrane factor", the phenomenon of epitaxis in the membrane should be given due consideration. The latter has been shown to be a dominant factor in membrane-transport processes in some biological systems as well⁴³⁻⁴⁵. Doubtless, the structure of the membrane and consequently the nature of its interaction with the diffusing species, are the determining factors of any membrane transport process, although the irreversible thermodynamic theory, discussed earlier can not provide any information of this kind, for the dependence of the phenomenological coefficients on the membrane-solution system is not specified.

There is strong evidence indicating the existence of epitaxed liquid and, in particular, "structured water" in hydrophilic membranes. Ordered water in living body was first reported by Cape⁴⁴ in rat muscles and brain through the use of nmr line broadening techniques. By similar means, Hazlewood *et al*⁴⁵ reported the existence of two types of ordered water in skeletal muscle. Recently, Froix and Goedda have studied the interaction of water with cellulose membrane⁴⁶ and the effect of temperature on this interaction⁴⁷, by means of nmr relaxation times. They have detected a drastic change in molecular mobility at the point of plasticization, which is characterised by the adsorption on the primary sites. They have further detected two types of water in the cellulose-water system : "bound" water and "free" water. The physical properties of both were changed drastically and the freezing point of bound water was found to be lowered to 196 K, and that of free water to between 221 K and 252 K.

Interaction of water with cellulose acetate membranes has also been studied, by, among other techniques, nmr and differential scanning calorimetry⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰, and the results indicate the presence of "unfrozen" but somewhat immobilised water in such membranes. Such "less mobile"

water need not be "ice-like" in structure as has been reported by recent infra-red studies on the state of water in cellulose acetate membranes by Toprak *et al*⁵¹. These workers have accounted for the observed salt-rejection by cellulose acetate membranes in reverse osmosis in terms of a low degree of association of water in contact with the membrane. The latter leads to a dissimilarity in the intermolecular structure and hydrogen bond strength of water molecules in cellulose acetate with those in the liquid water and this is proposed to be responsible for salt-exclusion.

In any event, what emerges is that the state of water, sorbed in various natural and synthetic polymer membranes is very different (whether weaker or stronger hydrogen-bonded than in pure liquid water) from that of liquid water.

(c) *Scope of radiation pressure theory* : In view of the interesting physico-chemical aspects of thermal diffusion and thermoosmosis as well as their apparent relevance in biology and other disciplines, the need of a more detailed and unified theoretical approach seems obvious. In this regard, the radiation pressure theory of Gaeta *et al* appears to be promising. It is generally thought that the thermal waves of liquids have frequencies of the order 10^9 to 10^{12} Hz. If their velocity of propagation in water is taken as 1500 m sec^{-1} , a simple calculation reveals that wavelengths, as short as several Å, are to be expected. This is certainly within macromolecular and perhaps even molecular dimensions and so the interaction between such thermal waves and solute particles seems plausible.

Before we conclude, mention must be made of the probable role thermoosmosis is expected to play in determining the membrane selectivities in solute transport and semipermeability of various cell membranes in living systems. Although the heat generated by various local metabolic changes is usually small, and may be dissipated before creating any effective temperature difference (for any appreciable period of time) between the two sides of a cell membrane, the actual temperature gradients across such membranes may be quite large in view of the extreme thinness of membranes in living systems. And, it is this temperature gradient which is the driving force for thermoosmotic flow. Some interesting work in this direction is being carried out by Gaeta and his school^{29, 52}. They claim to have explained the hypothesis of "sodium-potassium pump" in living systems on the basis of the radiation pressure theory they have advanced. However, it appears that much more remains to be done to this goal before anything, one way or the other, can be said with confidence.

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